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Fit for Purpose? Engineering Educators', Teacher Training & Engineering Scholarship

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FOREWORD: *The Engineering EDGE Project:* *The Study to which this paper refers to work that was undertaken by a collaboration of Engineering Educators from the UK & Ireland Engineering Education Research Network. Colleagues from 10 Engineering Departments contributed to the research tools and data collection. In alphabetical order, these colleagues are: Dr Esat Alpay (University of Surrey): Dr Jane Andrews (Aston University and then University of Warwick): Dr Jude Breton (University of York): Professor Robin Clark (University of Warwick): Professor John Davies (University of Liverpool): Manish Malik (University of Portsmouth): Dr Anne Nortcliffe (Christchurch Canterbury University): Ahn Tran (Coventry University): Dr Roger Penlington, (Northumbria University, Newcastle): Dr Peter Wilmott (Loughborough University). Additionally two colleagues have contributed towards parts of the analysis: Graeme Knowles, (University of Warwick) & Dr Suki Phull (Aston University).*

ABSTRACT

Drawing upon a small part of the findings of a large mixed-methodological research study, this paper starts by asking the controversial research question “Are Engineering Educators fit for Purpose?” In answering this question the study itself began with a critical analysis of the literature, something that is reflected in this paper. The articulation and definition of 12 key Engineering Skills, Competencies and Knowledge was undertaken at the beginning of the project based upon the undergraduate engineering curriculum taught at the 10 partner institutions.

Starting with the somewhat controversial research question “Are Engineering Educators’ fit for Purpose?” this paper has some important implications for how Engineering academics are supported and trained to teach. It critically discusses the study findings and concludes by suggesting that it is high time that the Postgraduate Certificate in Education and HEA Fellowship Programme were both adapted so as to account for the distinctive issues associated with teaching Engineering & Applied Science.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deservedly viewed as a subject of considerable importance for the continued sustainability of our society, engineering has an invaluable role to play in the global drive towards a poverty free, equitable world in which each individual has access to the latest technological advances that engineering, science and medicine are able to offer. To assure a continual flow of well-trained young people able to work within today’s fast-moving global engineering industry, university level Engineering Education is crucial for the development and dissemination of cutting edge engineering ideas, innovations and inventions. Yet, with increasing pressure on universities to provide a cost-effective, relevant and engaging education in which increasing numbers of students are offered high quality, individual educational experiences, the massification of Higher Education over the past two to three decades has resulted in Engineering Educators’ progressively finding themselves subject to a multiplicity of simultaneous demands and expectations. The results of such unprecedented increased work levels in terms of colleagues’ confidence to teach to a high standard remains largely undiscussed in the literature. It is this gap in knowledge that this paper addresses.

Set at a time when university level Engineering Education in across Europe and the globe is expected to satisfy the demands of a range of different stakeholders including current and future students, industry and employers, Professional Bodies, governments and universities, this paper represents an important turning-point in how Engineering Educators’ experiences are viewed and recorded. Looking specifically at how individual colleagues facilitate the development of their individual professional and educational expertise, the purpose of the study was initially to explore and analyse

the stresses associated with being an Engineering Educator. One of the most important variables examined was that of **'being trained to teach'**. It is this variable which is cross-tabulated with **'confidence in teaching key engineering skills'** and examined in this paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature covered in this paper is naturally limited when compared to the whole study. However, the two issues which are examined are both of high importance in setting the context for the data presented and issues discussed.

2.1 What is Engineering Education?

Representing the teaching of a mixture of engineering and scientific skills, competencies and concepts, contextualised across and within a divergent range of socio-economic, environmental and academic settings Engineering Education is somewhat difficult to define. Yet, when viewed holistically across a wide-range of educational and discipline specific sources of knowledge the literature begins to provide a sense of what the 'large and unwieldy discipline' that is Engineering Education actually is. For the purposes of the study upon which this paper is based the following definition was developed: *"Engineering Education involves a dualistic learning relationship in which engineering educators provide students with the means to acquire and hone a range of technical, practical and transferable competencies and skills with which to solve complex social, scientific and environmental problems"¹*.

A synthesis of core engineering, scientific and mathematical theories and concepts, university level Engineering Education needs to go beyond merely training new engineers. Indeed it needs to provide the ideal environment in which individual students can develop their creativity and critical thinking skills to adapt to a multi-disciplinary working environment in which they are able to use a range of complex higher order thinking skills and abilities to play a vital and continually changing role at the heart of our society^[2,3,4,5]

2.2 Barriers to High Quality Engineering Education

The Engineering Education Research literature identifies a number of **teaching-related** barriers to the provision of high quality learning and teaching within the discipline. Such barriers include: Poor levels of knowledge amongst engineering colleagues with regards to the breadth and depth of available innovative and evidence-based teaching methods: Time pressures within the academic environment meaning there simply isn't sufficient time for colleagues to spend on professional development in education: A lack of teaching skills and abilities in some colleagues: Shortages of innovative teaching resources, facilities and support for colleagues: Resistance to change by some individual lecturers: Constraints reflective of public and policy

impacting student numbers, course design and funding: Inconsistencies and a lack of transparency within individual institutions in terms of tenure and promotion: The type and focus of individual institutions, particularly with regards to a tendency to favour research over teaching: Issues surrounding teaching evaluation, government measures such as the NSS, PTES and TEF: Excessive workloads, and a lack of recognition and reward for excellent teaching^[6,7,8].

In addition to the above, a significant portion of the Engineering Education literature focuses on **student perceptions** of the barriers to high quality learning in engineering. This literature which suggests that the majority of students entering university to study engineering do so with little prior experience or knowledge of what the subject is about or what studying engineering will entail^[9]. Other studies suggest that students' perceive that there are a number of **lecturer-focused** barriers to high quality learning in Engineering Education including: Poor explanations of key engineering concepts and theories in lectures: A lack of clarity in assessment: A failure to provide high quality feedback: Low quality learning materials: Failure to recognise good quality student work^[10,11,12]

Whilst students' perspectives are generally limited to their immediate circumstances and will undoubtedly reflect individual experiences, prejudices and difficulties, there can be little argument that many Engineering Educators fail to engage with evidence-based teaching practice; remaining isolated from mainstream pedagogic theory and in some cases avoiding training programmes offered within institutions. Indeed, it is not unreasonable to note that rather than try and introduce innovation in the classroom, a considerable number of Engineering Educators prefer instead to continue with tried and tested 'traditional' teaching methods many of which fail to address the distinctive needs of today's learners^[13]. It is this reluctance, combined with a curiosity amongst the Project Team to closely examine the academic validity of current Engineering Education that led to the somewhat controversial research question of "*Are Engineering Educators fit for Purpose?*".

3. METHODOLOGY

Utilising a Design Based Research approach^[14] the Engineering EDGE Project brought together colleagues from 10 different Engineering Schools & Departments from different UK Universities. The Project had four distinctive stages:

1. Project Design: A Critical Literature Review: Development & piloting of research tools:
2. Quantitative Survey: 174 colleagues from across the Engineering Education Sector were sampled:
3. Qualitative Interviews and Analysis: 42 colleagues were interviewed from 15 HEIs:
4. Meta-Analysis and write-up.

The findings discussed in this paper relate to the second stage of the project and focus on a cross tabulation of two variables, the dependent variable of *colleagues confidence in teaching key skills and competencies* and the independent variable of *the level of teacher training colleagues had undertaken*. Other independent variables cross-tabulated against the analysis colleagues' confidence included: *Age: Gender: Level of Student Taught*.

3.1 Sample: Quantitative Study

A total of 174 colleagues were sampled equating to 34.8% of the sampling field of 500. The majority of those sampled were from an Engineering background and aged between 40 and 59 years of age. Figure 2 reveals the participants' demographic details showing that the majority (97%) were of an Engineering or Applied Science (Maths / Physics / Chemistry) background.

Figure 1: Sample Demographics (Quantitative Survey – Percentage of Sample).

Area	%	Age	%	Gender	%
West Midlands	33	Under 25	0	Male	70
Northern England	15	25-39	29	Female	30
East Midlands	13	40-49	29	Total %	100
South West England	11	50-59	31	Discipline	%
South East England	10	60-69	8	Engineering & Applied Science	97
Ireland, Scotland, Wales	9	70+	3	Business, Humanities & Social Science	3
Outside UK	9			Total	100
Total (Location)	100	Total	100		

3.2 Survey Question Focus

Working together looking at the engineering curriculum within each of the 10 institutions included in the study 12 key 'Engineering Skills, Competencies and Knowledge' were identified as being pivotal to success in Engineering, these were divided into two distinctive groups 'Engineering-Specific' and 'Transferable-Engineering'. These are shown overleaf in Figure 2.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the 12 key skills, competencies and knowledge tested (abbreviated to 'skills' for the purpose of the paper). A full description of each of these skills, based on the literature, is given in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 2: Key Engineering Skills & Competencies Pivotal to Success in Engineering

Engineering Specific Skills	Transferable Engineering Skills
Engineering Problem Identification	Creative Design
Building Things	Ability to be Adaptable
Ability to Make things Work	Critical Problem Solving
Optimisation Abilities	Spatial Visualisation
Discipline Specific Engineering Knowledge	Systems Thinking
Competence in Applying Technical Engineering & Scientific Knowledge	Ability to Contextualise Engineering within Society.

Whilst all of the above skills are relevant to Engineering, those identified as ‘Transferable Engineering Skills’ can be equally applicable to students from a range of backgrounds, albeit in different contexts and settings.

3.3 Analysis Techniques

The survey required colleagues to rate their own level of confidence in teaching the 12 key Engineering Specific Skills and Transferable Engineering Competencies identified in Figure 2 (and fully described in Figures 3 and 4). ‘Very Confident’ was coded as ‘5’ and ‘Somewhat Confident’ as ‘4’ (whilst totally lacking in confidence was coded as 1). During the analysis the data rated at 4 and 5 were merged and identified as indicating a level of Confidence.

For the part of the study discussed in this paper, ‘Confidence in Teaching’ was identified as the Independent Variable and a cross-tabulation undertaken in which it was measured against the Dependent Variable of being “Trained to Teach”. The negative hypothesis “*Being trained to teach **does not** impact Engineering Educators’ confidence in teaching*” was tested using Chi Square and calculating ‘*p*’. Because of wording restrictions in writing this paper, the decision was made that the readership will be better served by the provision of a full definition of each skill (grounded in the literature) than the inclusion of additional tables depicting Chi square and ‘P’ values (although these are available from the researchers if required). It should be noted that ‘Optimisation Abilities’ proved extremely difficult to academically define as there is a lack of research focusing on this particular Engineering Specific Skill / Competency. Hence, the research team itself defined ‘Optimisation Abilities in Engineering’ based on the industrial and academic engineering focused work experiences, insights and knowledge of colleagues on the team who between them have hundreds of years of

engineering experience in industry and academia. All of the other skills are fully referenced and academically defined.

Figure 3 in the following section reveals that for five of the key skills and competencies, the possession of a Teaching Qualification is **not** a significant factor influencing colleagues' confidence in teaching. Whilst Figure 4 shows the seven skills and competencies where Being Trained to Teach is a significant factor impacting confidence (although not necessarily in a positive manner)

4. SURVEY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Does being 'trained to teach' matter in terms of colleagues' confidence in teaching?

The study revealed that being trained to teach or possessing professional recognition in teaching **did not** significantly impact colleagues' confidence in teaching three of the 'Engineering-Specific' and two of the 'Transferable Engineering' skills (see Figure 3 overleaf).

The three 'Engineering Specific' skills where being trained to teach does not significantly impact confidence in teaching are: Engineering Problem Identification: The Ability to Make Things Work, and: Optimisation Abilities. It is interesting to note that these skills are not covered by generic postgraduate teaching programmes or professional recognition. Indeed, as noted earlier, the specialised nature of Optimisation Abilities within Engineering is rarely discussed even in the Engineering Education Literature. It is hardly surprising that it does not figure in generic teacher training. Moreover, it appears that engineering colleagues simply assume that all engineers know what this skill is (although how to teach it is a different matter altogether). Likewise, the two 'Transferable Engineering Skills' of 'The Ability to be Adaptable' and 'Systems Thinking' are rarely discussed in generic teacher training in Higher Education.

Figure 3: Confidence in Teaching Key Engineering Skills & Teacher Training (Where being trained to teach **IS NOT** significant factor determining confidence: C = Confidence [% of sample]).

Engineering Specific or Transferable Engineering skill.	DEFINITION	C %
Engineering Problem Identification: ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	The ability to use core engineering theories and knowledge to firstly identify and articulate what the issue is before going onto assess whether solutions are already exist. Engineers view problem finding as an opportunity and a challenges, with each new problem acting as a stimulus for innovation and invention ^[15,16]	90
Ability to be Adaptable TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	<i>The ability to work across disciplines and to empathise with others' experiences and perspectives. For Engineering students this means learning how to apply scientific and engineering principles to identify, analyse and explain how things work combined with a personal ability to be pliable in how engineering tasks, problems and theories are approached^[17,18]</i>	82

Systems Thinking TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	Systems thinking requires students to view complex problems and situations rigorously and holistically. Using systems thinking, professional engineers are able to recognise interdependencies, connectivity, patterns and linkages across and between problems, processes and practice ^[19,20]	70
Ability to Make things Work ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	<i>Having applied appropriate technical knowledge to a given engineering problem, engineering students learn how to utilise key practical engineering skills to assure that engineering artefacts, tools and models are fit for purpose and in working order^[21]</i>	70
Optimisation Abilities ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	A unique engineering skill in which engineering knowledge, skills and technology are applied in such a way so as to create high levels of synergy assuring engineering artefacts, tools and models operate at optimal levels	56

Whilst the skills listed and defined in Figure 3 are not influenced by whether colleagues are trained to teach, confidence in the remaining 7 skills listed and defined in Figure 4 are. Amongst these are the Engineering Specific Skills of: Competence in applying technical knowledge: The ability to correctly interpret and apply discipline specific engineering knowledge: and: Building things. Each of these three Engineering Specific skills, whilst generally not referred to in teacher training, require high levels of confidence and competence to teach as well as specialised levels of technical knowledge. That over half of the sample were not confident in teaching how to ‘build things’ is a matter of some concern given the hands-on nature of engineering. Likewise, the link between teaching training and colleagues’ confidence in teaching the four ‘Transferable Engineering Skills’ identified in Figure 4 is not necessarily a positive one.

Figure 4: Confidence in Teaching Key Engineering Skills & Teacher Training (Where being trained to teach **IS** a significant factor determining confidence [C = Confidence % of sample]).

Engineering Focused Or Transferable Engineering S	DEFINITION	C %
Critical Problem Solving TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	The ability to analyse problems and situations in a critical, logical & innovative manner. For engineering students this means being able to apply workable and logical solutions to a wide-range of technical, social and environmental problems so of which are yet to emerge ^[22] .	95
Ability to Contextualise Engineering within Society TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	Contextualise engineering problems, issues and challenges within wider society. Engineering students need to learn how to make sure that all engineering artefacts, tools and models are fit for purpose and accessible to the society for which they have been developed. Students also need to be able to communicate key engineering and scientific theories and concepts across all levels of society ^[23] .	95
Competence in Applying Technical Knowledge ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	The ability to apply technical engineering and scientific knowledge to problems occurring within the constructed or natural environmental in order to develop, test and implement practical and workable solutions ^[24]	91
Correctly interpret and apply Discipline Specific Engineering Knowledge ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	Provide evidence of an ability to understand , interpret and apply discipline-specific engineering, scientific and mathematical knowledge to technical, environmental and societal challenges. Student Engineers should be able to draw upon appropriate levels of discipline specific knowledge independently and apply it to given situations or challenges ^[25,26]	84
Creative Design TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	The ability to think ‘out of the box’ to imagine, design and create . For engineering students this involves a cognitive process culminating in the generation of an idea which is then applied to a design setting or engineering problem ^[27]	62

Building Things ENGINEERING SPECIFIC SKILL	The ability to construct scientifically appropriate engineering artefacts, tools and models for use in everyday situations by those with no specialist knowledge ^[28]	48
Spatial Visualisation TRANSFERABLE ENGINEERING SKILL	Whilst the ability to be able to view a given situation, model or artefact in 3 or 4 dimensions is essential across disciplines, in Engineering Spatial Visualisation requires being able to recognise the identity of an object when viewed from different angles. This means being able to imagine the movement or internal displacement amongst parts of a given configuration or object. In applying spatial visualisation, student engineers are taught how to be able to conceptualise spatial relations and linkages at the root of a particular problem, challenge or issue ^[29]	44

That only 44% of the sample were confident in their ability to teach ‘Spatial Visualisation’ and only 62% were confident in teaching ‘Creative Design’ says much about the focus and content of ‘Teacher Training’ and ‘Professional Development’ in Higher Education supporting arguments that there is a need to introduce specialised Teacher Training for those working in Engineering & Applied Science. Moreover, that none of the skills had a 100% confidence rating amongst the sample is something which requires serious thought and further investigation.

The results from the survey were used to guide and inform semi-structured interviews with 40 colleagues which sought to examine in some depth the various factors influencing colleagues’ lived experiences of teaching engineering. The qualitative findings together with a summary of the findings of a meta-analysis of the whole project are reported elsewhere^[30]

5. CONCLUSION: IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

This paper represents a small part of a much larger study which set out to investigate whether *Engineering Educators are fit for purpose*. In looking at the data presented here the question becomes not one of whether Engineering Educators are fit to practice or not but one of ***whether Teacher Training for and of Engineering Educators working in Higher Education is fit for purpose?***

The data suggests in the areas where confidence is not impacted by Teacher Training the specialised nature of Engineering Education means that the skills in this category would generally not be covered by generic teacher training. Likewise, where confidence is impacted by Teacher Training, the more technical or engineering specific skills are not covered in any current Postgraduate Certificate in Education or Professional Recognition Programmes.

The reasons for this are complicated, whilst both PG Certificates and Fellowship of the Higher Education Academy are purposefully focused widely so as to incorporate colleagues from across all disciplines, there is a strong case to argue that both types of training tend to be constructed so as to address the teaching needs of non-engineers and applied scientists. Indeed, it is not unreasonable to postulate that most

Educationalists responsible for developing and running such programmes originate from a non-scientific or engineering background.

There clearly is a need for change. The requirement that all of those teaching in Higher Education undergo a period of professional development or teacher training is not unreasonable; indeed, it should be lauded for its potential to enhance learning quality. However, the distinctive nature of Engineering & Applied Science Education means that many colleagues are not being given the tools, skills or resources to teach what are often perceived by students to be 'hard subjects'.

In conclusion, Engineering & Applied Science Education differs greatly from Business, Social Science & Humanities; likewise, it also differs from Medicine and the Natural Sciences. Year after year it seems that the NSS places levels of student satisfaction in Engineering below that of other disciplines in the UK. Whilst this is widely known, it is rarely discussed and the potential reasons for the deficit simply ignored. The data presented in this paper suggests there is a clear problem with *how we train Engineering Educators to teach*. It is high time that those responsible for teaching tomorrow's Engineering Professionals (and others working in the Applied Sciences and associated disciplines) were given support and recognition for the uniqueness and importance of the task in hand. The time is ripe for a redevelopment of Teacher Training. Key stakeholders from Engineering Education, the Professional (Engineering) Bodies and Industry need to get together to challenge the status quo and demand the introduction of bespoke, Engineering Education Teacher Training that is fit for the 21st Century!

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